

Capacity Needs Between Developmental Stages of Integrated Data Systems

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The United States has a fragmented system of programs and services supporting children and families, but as more states work to build comprehensive early care and education systems the desire to use integrated data as a tool for decision-making has become prevalent (Culhane et al., 2010; Little et al., 2019). More than 40 states have efforts underway to develop an early childhood integrated data system (ECIDS) that “collects, integrates, maintains, stores, and reports information from early childhood programs across multiple agencies within a state that serves children and families from birth to age eight” (Coffey et al., 2014, p.1). According to a national study, each ECIDS varies in the level of information gathered across administrative data systems to inform programmatic decisions about children and families receiving comprehensive services across multiple early childhood programs (Coffey et al., 2023a). The ECIDS does not replace the administrative data systems of a single program such as Head Start, one of many federally funded programs serving children under five in the United States (US). Rather, it maximizes the utility of data typically used only for reporting or establishing eligibility for participation in services, providing a more complete understanding of early childhood across a state. Ultimately, an ECIDS is designed to support the use of data for program and policy decisions by bringing together information from separate, siloed administrative systems and multiple state agencies to support decision-making for programs and services supporting children and families (Coffey et al., 2014).

Prior to implementing an ECIDS, states accessing information across programs or data sources for research and decision-making was slow and labor-intensive, and could take months or years, rendering the information neither relevant nor timely when findings were released and

often delayed due to legal challenges (Petrila, 2018). Now, state administrators are building the capacity to use statewide administrative data to inform program and policy decisions (Sirinides et al., 2024). Using an ECIDS, they can intentionally increase the use of existing administrative data systems by multiple stakeholders, policymakers, parents, community members, and educators who can make informed and efficient decisions that affect programs and policies for children and families (Keller et al., 2017). The United States is not the only country working on such projects. Ontario, Canada has been working on similar projects to the ECIDS, linking early childhood developmental outcomes with longitudinal student achievement data to develop a database that can be used to inform policies and practices and also linking early childhood and health data to better understand risk factors for early childhood issues (Saunders et al., 2021; Sinclair, Davies, & Janus, 2023). Australia is also working to link early childhood health and education data to inform practices and policies surrounding early childhood welfare (Taylor et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2024).

Although there is research on administrative data in other fields (e.g., criminal justice, social welfare, health) (DeHart and Shapiro, 2017; Kessel et al., 2014; Kitzmiller, 2014), there is a significant gap in research on integrated data systems regardless of the field. Though scholars have studied administrative data integration, general themes and patterns discovered have been broad, including concerns over data privacy (Kessel et al., 2014; Park, 2021; Walker et al., 2022), technological barriers to integrating administrative data (Culhane et al., 2018; Susha, 2023), and the logistics of the sustainability of integrated data systems (Culhane et al., 2010; Kitzmiller, 2014; Zanti et al., 2021). However, there is one thing that is consistent across time and disciplines, the idea that integrated data systems will aid in evidence-based policymaking. When administrative data are not used to their full potential, this prevents evidence-based

policymaking and reduces the evaluation of government programs (Culhane et al., 2010; Gibbs et al., 2017; Petrilă 2018). This is not unique to the United States as demonstrated by the global interest in integrating early childhood data and creating systems, however, there is a gap in understanding the capacity of government agencies when implementing sustainable systems to inform program and policy decisions. This study responds to the gap in the literature, particularly focusing on early childhood education, and begins to provide a foundation for evidence-based practices when creating data systems to inform public programs and policies.

Stages of Development

Integrating data across multiple existing data systems is a complex development process that is technical and programmatic. As such, there is no individual set of stages that appropriately depict the progress of an ECIDS. Given the limited research on the process of integrating early childhood data, insights from project management, data life cycles, and implementation science inform the stages that align with the development of an ECIDS. Although project management is needed for a large-scale project, project management stages come to an end (Project Management Body of Knowledge, 2021), an ECIDS is not a project that will ever be complete because data will continuously be integrated and used by state agencies. Given the iterative nature of this work, the stages of development can leverage technical processes referred to as data life cycles. There are numerous data life cycles, that demonstrate the continuous and reflect the nature of ECIDS development ranging from five to more than eight stages that include the following a variation of the following stages: requirement analysis, design, development and testing, implementation, documentation, and evaluation (McGilvray, 2021; Sebastian-Coleman, 2022). These stages of development focus on the implementation as communicated through technical requirements and also end when the product is complete, but additionally do not

capture the program and stakeholder engagement for the use of the data. The four stages of Active Implementation Research, exploration, installation, initial implementation, and the full implementation, address the data life cycle gaps by addressing the program and stakeholder engagement and recognizing that it is a non-linear process (Fixen et al., 2005; Metz & Bartley, 2012), but the ECIDS is not a program. Ultimately program management, technical data life cycles, and the Active Implementation Framework together provide a critical part of the ECIDS stages of development, but individually they do not capture the nature of progress made when integrating data systems to be used to inform program and policy decisions.

As highlighted by Zanti and Thomas (2021), who looked at more than 100 frameworks used in implementation science, context should drive the decision about which framework to use to develop and implement an integrated data system. When looking across relevant frameworks from project management, technology development, and implementation science, four major stages capture the broader implementation stages appropriate for ECIDS implementation: Considering/exploring whether to pursue ECIDS work (not actively planning an ECIDS, but gathering information about options to do so), planning an ECIDS (in the process of planning ECIDS), developing (actively in the process of integrating data, developing the data model, piloting the integration process), and operating (ECIDS is operational, and the state or territory is actively working to add/enhance their ECIDS, or simply maintaining with no plans to enhance the ECIDS). The four stages of ECIDS development (considering, planning, developing, and operating) outline the process for implementing the ECIDS and we can see 3 critical transition points where programs can falter across the developmental stages of the ECIDS: considering to planning, planning to developing, and developing to operating. Currently, 13% of states are

considering, 27% are planning, 30% are developing, and 30% are operating (Coffey et al, 2023b). The rest of this paper explores which factors enable states to advance stages.

Capacities Areas Driving Successful Transitions Between Stages

Due to the scant research in early childhood education about the capacities needed to develop early childhood integrated data systems, we drew upon previous work on the relevant capacity areas in integrated data systems (IDS), such as the Tiered IDS Capacity model (Sirinides et al., 2024), as well as research from implementation science, to investigate which capacities are most critical to successful transitions through stages. Active Implementation Framework drivers are often used in research that is focused on understanding implementation in various contexts (Metz & Albers, 2014; Metz & Bartley, 2012; Metz et al., 2013; Metz et al., 2015;), program infrastructure and systems alignment (Metz et al., 2013), and what is needed move development forward (Nilsen, 2015; Zanti & Thomas, 2021).

Competency Drivers within IDS

Competency drivers are “mechanisms to develop, improve, and sustain practitioners’ and supervisors’ ability to implement a program or innovation to benefit children and families” (Metz & Bartley, 2012). Competency drivers focus on the human capital needed for a successful program. Examples of indicators described by Metz et al., (2013) include having dedicated staff in charge of hiring new staff members who align with the program’s mission, having robust training techniques in place for new staff members, and/or having thorough assessment practices to evaluate new staff members. Indicators of competency drivers are important for an ECIDS and are found to be the critical human capacity needed to implement an IDS (Kitzmilller, 2014; Allison-Jacobs, 2018; Sirinides et al., 2024).

Organizational Drivers with IDS

Organization drivers, “intentionally develop the organizational supports and systems interventions needed to create a hospitable environment for new programs and innovations by ensuring that the competency drivers are accessible and effective and that data are used for continuous improvements” (Metz & Bartley, 2012, p. 14). While competency drivers focus on the individual-level supports needed for program success, organizational drivers emphasize the organizational-level supports needed, such as organizational data, facilitative administration, and systems interventions (Metz & Bartley, 2012; Metz et al., 2013). Similar to the organizational drivers, Sirinides et al. (2024) found that capacity relating to Organizational Learning (OL) conditions is important to building staff engagement and professional skills related to ECIDS development. Additionally, when implementing an ECIDS, technical scalability and resiliency is also a necessary capacity area (Sirinides et al., 2024) because a technical solution will be needed to collect, store, and report the data while maintaining multi-system involvement through adapting to the changes in technological systems.

Leadership Drivers with IDS

Leadership drivers relate to understanding what strategies are best to address challenges of program implementation by the leaders at the multiple systems levels (Fixen et al., 2018; Metz et al., 2013). Sirinides et al. (2023), reported three key project leadership roles: ECIDS/project, technical, and analytic, but these roles are situated within state agencies with senior leadership as well as states led by governors. Within IDS research, leadership drivers were found in two IDS capacity categories: governance and decision authority and (2) systems alignment and coordination (Sirinides et al., 2024).

The Tiered IDS Capacity Model's five capacity areas aligned with the drivers of the active implementation framework provide a framework this study seeks to understand what capacities are needed to transition between one ECIDS developmental stage and the next: Human Capital Development (as competency drivers), Organizational Learning Conditions, Technical Resilience and Scalability (as organizational drivers), Data Governance and Decision Authority, and Systems Alignment and Coordination (as leadership drivers) help to understand what may impacts state agencies as they work to transition from one stage of ECIDS development to the next.

Research Questions

1. How does capacity influence a state's progression through the development stages of the ECIDS?
2. Given the identified implementation capacity areas, where are the challenges states encounter when building capacity to transition between stages?

Method

A complementary mixed-methods design (Greene, 2007) was employed to answer the research questions in this study. Integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis supported the research interests of understanding the transitions between stages of ECIDS development and the challenges states experience. A survey comprised of quantitative and qualitative items was administered to states and territory administrators managing the ECIDS effort followed by interviews with state teams.

Participants

A purposive sampling strategy was used to recruit participants for this study. The participants of the study were those who were responsible for overseeing the development of an ECIDS in their state. In most cases that was the ECIDS lead, but in other cases the Preschool

Development Grant Birth through Five manager or a technical lead for the work completed the survey. Using email addresses maintained for each state administrator managing the ECIDS, participants were contacted twice over email from June through September 2022, using the Qualtrics web-based survey system. All states and territories that are considering or working towards an ECIDS (historically, or currently) were recruited to participate (N=51) and 30 (58.8%) state leads participated in the study. Of the 30 that participated in the study, all were invited to participate in a follow-up interview and 16 agreed to participate in 60-minute semi-structured interviews. Several ECIDS team leaders invited additional staff members to join the interview to ensure that information outside of their expertise could be provided. Of the 16 completed interviews, 8 were conducted with an ECIDS team of two or more individuals, usually an ECIDS lead along with an analytic lead. Most participants who did not have a team join them on the call identified as having a role spanning multiple responsibilities but were typically identified as the ECIDS lead. Because of the variety of team members per call, we will refer to the interviews as being done with “states” rather than individuals. To deidentify the participants, states were assigned a random number, then sorted according to the random number they were assigned, and will subsequently be referred to as “State number” when discussed in the results section.

Survey Data Collection

The survey consisted of 31 closed and four open-ended response items for a total of 35 questions. The survey was administered using Qualtrics and included the necessary logic to administer the survey to save time for states when responding. The survey asked detailed questions about the staffing structure for the ECIDS teams, how the ECIDS aligned with other state system initiatives and early childhood policy priorities, technical design, and organizational

support available to the team. We piloted the survey with three states, one in each stage of development: planning, developing, and operating. Each state that helped pilot the survey met with the research team for 60 minutes to provide feedback on the clarity of the questions, content options for multiple select questions, and items that would be useful to know the results in their work developing an ECIDS. Based on feedback during the pilot, the research team updated the survey.

Interview Data Collection

The semi-structured interviews were 60 minutes with either an individual or in some cases a state team of two or more. All interviews were virtual, conducted using Zoom software, and with participants' consent, all interviews were recorded and transcribed. The interviews were guided by 19 questions designed to gather information about states' experiences with planning, building, implementing, and funding an ECIDS such as, "What state supports do you receive that influenced your ability to develop and implement an ECIDS?" Questions were designed to gather successes and challenges at each system level and the area of capacity. The interviews were conducted by one researcher, with one additional member of the research team present at the interviews to take notes. Following, the interviews were transcribed using REV Human Transcription services.

Data Analysis

Our study explored states' transition to higher stages of ECIDS development, conditional on their implementation capacity, using binary logistic regression across three models. Each model shared the same specification but differed in outcome variables, coded as one if the state had reached the higher developmental stage. The analysis focused on the likelihood of

transitioning based on capacity variables and calculated marginal effects for capacity type and system level (Sirinides, et al., 2024).

Data were structured in long format comprising 450 records for 30 states, including identifiers and binary capacity variables. Records were further classified by type and system level, and interactions were analyzed. The response variable was modeled as a binary distribution using the logit link function, employing the Laplace method for parameter estimates. This approach enabled us to explore the likelihood of transitioning to a higher stage based on capacity variables as well as the marginal effects for capacity type and system level.

A Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) approach with a random intercept term for each state was employed to address correlations within state capacities, using robust standard errors to enhance inference validity.

$$\log\left(\frac{p_{ij}}{1-p_{ij}}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Capacity}_{ij} \text{Type}_{0j} + \beta_2 \text{Capacity}_{ij} \text{Level}_{0j} + u_{0j}$$

The logistic regression model related capacity indicators to state transition probabilities, and post hoc tests estimated marginal means and computed odds ratios, offering insight into the impact of capacity variables on transition probabilities.

To better understand the challenges state administrators experience during transitions, the interview data was analyzed using NVivo (version 13). All interview data was transcribed verbatim and read through twice in their entirety before any coding. Each stage of coding was initially completed by one member of the research team and subsequently reviewed by another member of the team before proceeding to the next step of coding. The initial coding cycle focused on categorizing the qualitative data, the research team coded in the following ways: (a)

structural, (b) subcode, and (c) initial. In the second cycle of coding the team used (a) provisional and (b) focused coding to make meaning from the data (Saldaña, 2021).

The first step in the qualitative analysis involved structural coding, which explored the data by reading the interview transcripts and identifying high-level codes that represented key concepts. The structural coding resulted in several broad categories, including approaches to the development of an ECIDS, references to early childhood system-building initiatives, ECIDS staffing, and resources supporting an ECIDS. These high-level codes were then analyzed for subcodes (e.g., types of ECIDS roles mentioned, data sharing, technical infrastructure, and funding). Initial coding was then used to look across state responses in the structural and subcode data. The cycle one coding provided rich context on state experiences developing an ECIDS.

Second-cycle coding was then used to further understand the expressed concerns from states as they moved from one stage of ECIDS development to another. First, the team used the Tiered IDS Capacity Model (Sirinides et al., 2024) to provisionally code the data according to the five areas of capacity building. Research team members then did a round of focused coding, identifying challenges in moving from one stage of development to the next and created a data display using the five capacity areas (rows) by each transition between states (e.g., considering to planning, planning to developing, developing to operating) (columns) was developed (Miles et al., 2014). Using this data display, thematic analysis was then used to understand the consistent challenges states experience when transitioning from one stage of ECIDS development to the next.

Results

Our investigation centered around understanding the likelihood of moving across ECIDS development stages based on factors within the ECIDS implementation capacity framework. The

findings presented in Table 1 offer a range of insights regarding specific capacity types and system levels significantly associated with transitions between stages within ECIDS development.

Table 1*Implementation Capacity by ECIDS Stage of Development*

	ECIDS Stages of Development				
	Considering	Planning	Developing	Operating	All
ECIDS Stage (n)	4	8	9	9	30
ECIDS Stage (%)	13%	27%	30%	30%	100%
Human Capital Development					
Specialized Staff	0%	13%	56%	89%	47%
Support Services	0%	63%	78%	89%	67%
Multisystem Engagement	25%	38%	67%	100%	63%
Governance & Decision Authority					
Formal Directives	25%	13%	67%	89%	53%
Data Governance	0%	0%	33%	89%	37%
System Adoption	0%	0%	22%	56%	23%
Org. Learning Conditions					
Feedback Culture	0%	0%	11%	44%	17%
Multidisciplinary Teaming	25%	13%	33%	56%	33%
Interagency Cooperation	25%	0%	22%	44%	23%
Tech. Scalability & Resilience					
Analytic Tools	100%	50%	67%	100%	77%
Data Partnerships	0%	13%	44%	56%	33%
Flexible Architecture	0%	0%	67%	44%	33%
System Alignment & Coord.					
Defined Objectives	0%	0%	11%	78%	27%
Inclusive Planning	25%	25%	44%	89%	50%
Program Integration	0%	0%	0%	56%	17%
Overall Capacity	15%	15%	41%	72%	40%

There are three transition points across the developmental stages of the ECIDS; considering to planning, planning to developing, and developing to operating. Table 2 shows the results.

Table 2*Capacities During Each Transition Between Developmental Stages*

	Transition to Planning		Transition to Developing		Transition to Operating	
	β (SE)	OR	β (SE)	OR	β (SE)	OR
Functional Capacities ^a						
Human Capital Development	1.66 (0.57)*	5.24 [1.70, 16.15]	1.22 (0.32)**	3.38 [1.80, 6.36]	1.44 (0.45)*	4.22 [1.75, 10.16]
Governance & Decision Authority	1.28 (0.59)*	3.60 [1.14, 11.39]	1.82 (0.40)**	6.20 [2.84, 13.56]	1.45 (0.31)**	4.26 [2.30, 7.87]
Organizational Learning Conditions	0.20 (0.39)	1.22 [0.57, 2.63]	0.92 (0.40)*	2.51 [1.15, 5.49]	1.03 (0.41)*	2.81 [1.25, 6.29]
Technical Scalability & Resilience	0.51 (0.17)*	1.67 [1.21, 2.32]	0.94 (0.23)**	2.55 [1.61, 4.04]	0.68 (0.27)*	1.97 [1.16, 3.32]
System Alignment & Coordination	0.78 (0.55)	2.18 [0.74, 6.44]	1.30 (0.35)**	3.66 [1.84, 7.26]	1.67 (0.26)**	5.29 [3.15, 8.87]
System Levels ^b						
ECIDS Project	0.56 (0.27)*	1.75 [1.03, 2.98]	1.14 (0.23)**	3.12 [2.0, 4.88]	1.40 (0.24)**	4.05 [2.55, 6.45]
Lead Agency	1.30 (0.40)*	3.68 [1.69, 8.05]	1.14 (0.18)**	3.14 [2.20, 4.47]	1.17 (0.22)**	3.23 [2.12, 4.94]
Cross-Agency	0.79 (0.26)*	2.21 [1.32, 3.68]	1.44 (0.25)**	4.20 [2.59, 6.82]	1.18 (0.31)**	3.27 [1.79, 5.98]

^a $df = 177$
^b $df = 124$
** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.05$, ~ $p < 0.10$

Transitioning from Considering to Planning Requires Human Capital

There are three key roles identified for the ECIDS: ECIDS project lead, IT lead, and analytics lead (Coffey et al., 2023a). Survey results showed that all states that have successfully created an operational ECIDS (33.3%) have an ECIDS lead. States that worked on an ECIDS without a designated lead (36.7%), or had an ECIDS lead that split time between responsibilities (30%) were not successfully able to move from the planning stages to implementation.

Additionally, the survey showed that states that are developing or operating are more likely to staff the capacity of a research lead (59%) than states considering or planning an ECIDS (8%).

Our research findings highlight the significant influence that investing in Human Capital

Development has on a state's ability to advance to the planning stage of ECIDS development (OR= 5.24, 95% CI [1.70, 16.15]). Specifically, states that invest in Human Capital Development have over five times greater odds of reaching the planning stage compared to states that do not make such investments. During the interviews, state administrators report challenges with turnover, funding, hiring timelines, competing priorities, and articulating the appropriate set of skills to influence the human capital development capacity.

Despite the increase in ECIDS leadership roles across states, turnover in these positions was a major concern for state agencies working to create an ECIDS. Of the states who participated in the interviews, the most reported reason for turnover was short-term funding associated with leadership positions (State 3, 7, 16).

Although, ECIDS teams are structured differently state-by-state. States that are earlier in the planning and development process might not have a large, functional team, whereas states that have fully implemented an ECIDS might have a team dedicated full-time to ECIDS work. For example, one interview participant, a state administrator who identified their ECIDS as being in the developing stage, had a team of four externally contracted, full-time people working on the system itself (a project manager, analyst, and two IT people), plus the ECIDS lead, 10 program leaders, three department data staff, and four administrators working part-time on the ECIDS project (State 9). Alternatively, all but one of the interview participants that are in the planning stages shared that they might only have one or two ECIDS staff dedicating a portion of their time to the ECIDS effort (States 3, 8, 14, 15, 16) Most states that have moved from the planning stages to the operating mentioned that not having a full staff from the beginning of the project was a challenge and would have made the ECIDS planning and development process much easier (States 4, 7, 10). Several participants in all areas of development echoed this, and

when asked about what they would have in an ideal world with no limitations, most states (75.0% of interview participants working on an ECIDS) mentioned and described several types of staffing positions they would like to see. These positions related to having a stable point of contact who could connect ECIDS stakeholders and state agencies (States 3, 16, 8, 10), having dedicated statisticians and data collection positions (States 2, 7, 11), generally describing skills they would like to see in a newly created position, such as both technical/IT skills and research skills (States 4, 9, 15), or simply mentioning some external consultants or university partners they would like to work with (States 12, 13).

Something state administrators in all stages of ECIDS implementation consistently emphasized is that having staff with the right skills is a crucial component in the ECIDS process. One interview participant, who is from a state where they are the only one on their team at the time of the interview, describes what type of individual they would look for to fill a staffing role on their team, stating,

“...project management is the biggest one, because as long as you can find the right expertise to draw in at the different times...what comes to mind is curiosity and initiative, because it’s not a concrete knowledge background, but you have to want to learn about data. You have to want to learn about IT, you have to want to figure out how to effectively facilitate a group of people. You have to have some interest in the policy questions. So as long as you’re curious and take the initiative then you can find the people that you need to bring in, like the IT expertise or the legal expertise” (State 15).

As the ECIDS advances into the developing and operating stages, interview participants describe how differentiated skills become critical such as project management, technical, analytics, and engagement/communications where in the planning stages it is not uncommon to have one person providing many of them until the system is built (States 3, 7 8, 15). Hiring in the planning stages already takes significant time, and then finding the right person with the skill set

to align to a project that evolves is challenging. In the developing stage, states mentioned in the interviews that vendors are often used to supplement state staff, but by the time the system is operational state staff struggle to transition ownership of the contracted skills which impacts the sustainability of the work (States 5, 6, 13).

Once staff have been identified and hired, several states report that team members report having to balance competing priorities and working to get attention from leadership who also have competing priorities. When staff are to the ECIDS they are often split across state data system initiatives and projects (States 3, 6, 7, 8, 15). Managing the human capital development needs for the ECIDS is a critical challenge across all states in this study. All interview participants articulated that more full-time positions should be created to make ECIDS sustainable long-term.

Transitioning from Planning to Developing Requires Governance and Authority

Our analysis underscores the critical importance of data governance and decision authority in progressing to the developing stage (OR= 6.20, 95% CI [2.84, 13.56]). States with robust decision-making structures exhibit a greater likelihood of reaching this intermediate stage of ECIDS development. State administrators, across all interviews, identified that getting beyond privacy and security, obtaining legal and leadership support to champion the data sharing agreements, and allocating appropriate resources to build the necessary infrastructure as the challenges they have in building the capacity for data governance and decision-making.

In the considering and planning stages of the ECIDS states report privacy and security being a key challenge (States 1, 2, 9, 12, 13). Not because the data are an issue as much as the potential risk and the inability to move past why the state would use the data they collect for anything beyond compliance reporting. States in the operating stage report this work early in the

planning stages as the largest hurdle and that it takes a long time to get past why the ECIDS is essential and how data will be protected (States 4, 5, 6, 7, 10). State leaders recommend, “start early and give it time” (State 14) because the process can be lengthy. Establishing the data-sharing agreements was particularly challenging for states that did not engage legal teams from the beginning or have the buy-in from state agency leadership to champion the agreements through completion (States 5, 12, 14, 15). When states do have support from their legal counsel, “their interpretation of the federal statute that dictates the parameters of privacy and confidentiality for a particular federal program” (State 1) can be restrictive when applied to an ECIDS.

Developing and leading the data governance for the ECIDS can be resource-intensive. One strategy that most state administrators who participated in the interviews reported that they employ to reduce the resource burden and ensure statewide alignment by coordinating with other statewide data governance efforts. Of the 16 states interviewed, 68.8% of interview participants mentioned alignment and coordination in some way. States in the coordinating and planning stages talked about initial conversations with statewide partners and identifying where the state resources might be (States 2, 6, 9, 10, 14, 15). The states in the operational stage shared various ways they are connected with statewide governance efforts (e.g., sharing policies) when they exist. That being said, not every state has a statewide data governance body to align with for support. In these cases, ECIDS staff must identify additional resources when there is not a statewide data governance body to leverage to reduce the burden. This leads to states relying on federal funding to develop the infrastructure for early childhood data governance and encourage participation in the decision-making processes, the state leaders report the gaps it causes when funding ends,

“when federal dollars went away, the support and capacity to maintain that body of work [data governance] also went away. So, tons of amazing work, and with the absence of something like a preschool development grant, that work was paused” (State 8).

Data governance and authority is challenging for an ECIDS because the states need it to move into the implementation stages, but it is difficult to build the infrastructure in a way that gets the attention necessary for making decisions when there are competing priorities, “It’s the amount of time and the strategy to engage the people who have sign off when they have so many other things on their plate” (State 15). The additional data governance challenge identified by state leaders is building the capacity for the infrastructure when both the executive and program staff are consistently turning over (States 3, 7, 8, 16).

Transitioning from Developing to Operating Requires Systems Alignment

For states that have advanced to the operating stage, our survey findings underscore the significance of System Alignment and Coordination (OR= 5.29, 95% CI [3.15, 8.87]). States that effectively align and coordinate their systems showcase increased odds of attaining this advanced phase of ECIDS development. State administrators report challenges in assessing the interests and use of an ECIDS, navigating between multiple policy bodies with different priorities, and lacking the ability to demonstrate value when the ECIDS (States 3, 7).

In the planning stages of the ECIDS, a tremendous amount of work goes into assessing the “appetite” for an ECIDS (States 1, 14). Interview participants report using statewide strategic plans to develop the use cases for the ECIDS, but often still have the challenge of finding the best-positioned state agency to lead the ECIDS development (States 12, 14, 15, 16) One state reports, “we need to find a home for [the ECIDS] in an agency” (State 15). Planning might live in one agency, such as the Department of Education, but implementation may require it to be

moved to a different state agency “home.” Thus, locating the appropriate for long-term implementation is a critical activity during the considering and planning stages, “I don’t think that anything in the implementation phase is going to be sustainable if it lives in this nebulous cross-agency effort” (State 15).

Operational ECIDS are more likely to be in a state with an established early childhood care and education system. When there is not one statewide early childhood governing body the ECIDS team reports a lack of strategic direction for the ECIDS and navigating between the possible program and policy leaders to determine the priorities delays the work. For example, State 3 stated, “So it's like we had the funding to do a thing so we used it, but we don't have a way to sustain the work. Which was a challenge...because you'd get a grant, it would come from one source that could only be used for one purpose. And then if somebody else had a need it was like everyone's competing, or work totally stops and nothing happens. And that's just not how these products work.” Also, in states where the policy priorities are established by different governing bodies (e.g., governors, legislators, agency leaders) and where there are competing policy priorities, ECIDS teams mentioned in the interviews that they experience significant delays or sometimes the development of the ECIDS is completely stopped (States 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 12, 15).

States in the development stage report the significant data gaps that exist and the impact on the ability to report data meaningful to the policy priorities of the state determined under the system-building initiatives of states (States 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 15). For example, states are very focused on addressing workforce shortages given low compensation and the pandemic but state agencies lack workforce data, “we don’t even have [data on] credentials” (State 11). Of the states with an ECIDS in developing or operating, survey results showed that 20% are linked to the

quality rating and improvement systems (QRIS), and 10% to the workforce registry, both are critical to current early childhood policy discussions.

ECIDS System Levels Capacity Affects Transitions

The findings of our analysis also underscore the crucial role of distinct capacity system levels in facilitating stage transitions. Of the three systems levels: ECIDS Project teams, lead agency, and cross-agency, we observe that capacity at the lead agency level serves as a pivotal determinant for entering the planning stage. When moving into the next stage, developing, the strength of the state's cross-agency efforts significantly influences the state's ability to progress. For states that have reached the operating stage in ECIDS, the capacity at the ECIDS project level emerges as a key predictor.

Discussion

Similar to other integrated data system efforts, an ECIDS is designed to provide relevant data to communities, parents, and state leaders to inform program and policy decisions (Coffey et al., 2014; Kitzmiller, 2014; Data Quality Campaign & The Early Childhood Data Collaborative, 2016; Keller et al., 2017; Walker et al., 2022; Susha, 2023). Those leading the ECIDS effort, however, have the impossible task of creating a data system without the resources for implementation. As seen in global research, investments have historically been made to link data for specific projects, but sustaining the linkage over time requires more infrastructure (Culhane et al., 2010; Gibbs et al., 2017; Zanti et al., 2021). This study reiterates that it is the operational components, not technology (Regenstein, 2022), that are holding states back from developing an ECIDS that provides relevant information to these audiences. Broomfield and Reutter (2021) highlight that even in other countries where technology is advanced is the implementation of integrated data being used in public administration is nascent. Understanding which capacities

are needed at which stages to achieve implementation can save time and resources as well as manage grant expectations and timeframes. This study may be useful to help state administrators assess the state's capacity to implement the ECIDS, manage community interest groups' expectations of timeline, and inform state teams' requests for appropriate levels of support from state leadership. The challenges identified by the state administrators are not insignificant and often delay, or completely stop, the ECIDS from moving to the next stage of development. Understanding that the essential capacity required for transitioning from one stage to the next varies at different points can assist states with prioritizing the necessary capacity needed to move to the next stage instead of attempting to move through all stages simultaneously. These empirical insights can potentially guide policy decisions, resource allocation, and targeted interventions aimed at fostering the advancement of ECIDS. This, in turn, may enable more informed and effective efforts to propel ECIDS development toward its highest potential.

Given that the results of this study demonstrate that human capital is necessary to begin planning an ECIDS, competencies need to be better defined to identify staff earlier in the ECIDS development process and retain the staff. Additionally, staff identified for the ECIDS face a significant learning curve. Not only do they need to understand the processes of their department but be able to work across their agency and other state agencies. The ECIDS staff benefit from previous experience navigating across groups within state government. It is encouraging that so many states have been able to move from the considering to planning stages and that we are seeing more staff hired specifically for the ECIDS implementation using both federal and state funding (Coffey et al., 2023b).

We also find that when moving from planning to developing, states need the capacity to support data governance. While data governance seems like a given in the development of any

IDS (Kitzmilller, 2014; Gibbs et al., 2017; Zanti et al., 2021), in early childhood education, the need to coordinate across agencies and in some cases more than twenty programs providing services to children and families can be a particular challenge. This work is resource intensive and not a given part of the work typically done by the state administrators. Not only is there a lack of infrastructure, but frequent staff turnover makes building the knowledge base and processes to implement data governance across state agencies difficult. To support building this capacity, states can look to leverage current statewide data-sharing policies as well as decision-making bodies that already exist in the state and processes from other statewide data system efforts such as the statewide longitudinal data system.

When transitioning between the stages of developing and operating, we find that states need capacity for systems' alignment and coordination. Although more than 40 states have, or are currently, working to create an ECIDS, becoming operational has been the most challenging stage for states due to gaps in alignment across state agencies setting the policy priorities. Without established cross-agency policy priorities, ECIDS teams cannot effectively provide information relevant to program and policy decisions. Specifically, the ECIDS is designed to inform the early childhood care and education statewide policy conversations typically driven by a coordinated system. The fragmented nature of early childhood care and education in the United States presents a unique challenge. The Preschool Development Grant Birth Through Five initiative was designed to support states in their effort to create a comprehensive system (Administration for Children and Families, 2022). Unfortunately, not all states have developed an effective cross-agency program and policy governance for an early childhood care and education (ECCE) comprehensive system (Kagan & Gomez, 2015) which limits the usability of the ECIDS and the ability to gather the needed resources to transition from one stage to the next,

specifically to become operational, as found in this study. As states continue to develop comprehensive systems, further research using systems evaluation could be used to better articulate the points of connection between the systems governance and the data governance necessary for an ECIDS to be successful.

While findings help to inform the priorities of state agencies working to create an ECIDS, there are limitations. First, to address the validity threats that accompany mixed-methods research, this study used triangulation to enhance credibility (Patton, 2015). The quantitative data presented the significance of each capacity area between stages of development and the qualitative data provided rich information about why those capacity areas were important or less important drivers of implementation which helped our team to validate the findings regarding our transition points. Second, in this study, we used the 15 capacity indicators as binary variables from survey responses using insights from state interviews. Given the limited research on ECIDS, it is uncertain whether these indicators are valid measures of the constructs represented in the Tiered IDS Capacity Model (Sirinides et al., 2024). While our approach underwent multiple stages of validation and revision, it is recommended that future research focus on refining the operational definitions of these capacity areas and evaluating the consistency of these measures. Third, the number of survey responses was limited. The size, however, accurately reflects the relatively small population of interest, comprising 60 states and territories. A modest sample size is anticipated and can still provide a representative view of the targeted population (Draugalis & Plaza, 2009; Hendra & Hill, 2019; Wu, Zhao, & Fils-Aime, 2022). For statistical analysis, we employed robust standard errors to enhance the rigor of the findings. Nevertheless, it is advisable for future research to not only replicate these findings within the ECIDS framework but also expand them to other IDS contexts.

It is also important to note that researcher bias had to be mitigated (Maxwell, 2013). We are a team of researchers who have worked with each state to create an ECIDS over the last decade. We have worked alongside many of the states and have first-hand experience of where there were challenges in transitions. We recognized that this was beneficial to the data collected in this study as we could ask rich questions of the participants to understand their experiences and for them to feel comfortable sharing their challenges, but we also know that it could lead to a bias when interpreting the data. We addressed this potential bias by introducing a new team member who has not worked directly with states. In addition, we used member checks (completed by states that both participated in the study and those that did not) to review the results of the study to validate the findings and challenge assumptions made by the research team (Bryman, 1988; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Additionally, when more than one state team member was in the interviews, we realized the threat of reactivity (Maxwell, 2013). There are dynamics across teams that may influence what one member says in front of other team members (Kvale, 2006). Given this was not a study looking at the dynamics within a team, we would note the information provided by various team members and ask supplemental questions to see if there was a different perspective on an experience from another team member.

There is potential for the significant value of an ECIDS to state agencies working to coordinate programs and services for children and families, but more research is needed to understand the implementation of these systems and the impact they have on informing policy and program decisions. Despite substantial federal and state investments in these data systems, there is little empirical research on state efforts to create an ECIDS. Current research has leveraged the data-driven decision-making (DDDM) research primarily used in primary and secondary educational settings for instructional purposes (Datnow et al., 2021; Mandinach &

Jackson, 2012; Mandinach & Schildkamp, 2021); and there are a few studies on DDDM in early childhood instruction (deMonsabert et al., 2021; Varier & Yun, 2023). The field would benefit from future research on integrated administrative data not only for instructional planning but also for policy and program decisions by public administrators. This study begins to highlight some of the implementation supports needed by the teams working to transition between one stage of implementation and the next, but more research is needed about the state capacity, ECCE governance models, and specific staff competencies needed for the sustainability of efforts and the return on the investments made into the ECIDS across the United States.

References

- Administration for Children and Families. (2022, October 24). *Preschool Development Grant Birth Through Five*. <https://www.acf.hhs.gov/ecl/early-learning/preschool-development-grants>
- Allison-Jacobs, R. (2018). IDS Case Study: The Institute for Social Capital – Creating a Hybrid IDS Model for the Greater Charlotte-Mecklenburg Region. Actionable Intelligence for Social Policy. <https://aisp.upenn.edu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/ISC.pdf>
- Broomfield, H., & Reutter, L. M. (2021). Towards a data-driven public administration: An empirical analysis of nascent phase implementation. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Administration*, 25(2), 73-97. <https://ntnuopen.ntnu.no/ntnu-xmlui/handle/11250/2980669>
- Bryman, A. (1988). *Quantity and Quality in Social Research*. Routledge.
- Coffey, M., Chatis, C., Irvine, S., Sellers, J., & Duarte, S. (2014). *An early childhood integrated data system: What is an ECIDS?* U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics.

- Coffey, M., Sirinides, P., & Dabbs, E. R. (2023b, August 9-11). *2022 Early childhood integrated data national study* [Conference session]. National Center for Education Statistics STATS-DC Data Conference, Washington, DC, United States.
- Coffey, M., Sirinides, P., Dabbs, E. R., & Havrilla, A. M. (2023a). *Building capacity to implement an ECIDS: Leadership staffing*. Pennsylvania State University. ECDataWorks.
- Culhane, D. P., Fantuzzo, J., Rouse, H. L., Tam, V., & Lukens, J. (2010). *Connecting the dots: The promise of integrated data systems for policy analysis and systems reform*. University of Pennsylvania. <https://repository.upenn.edu/handle/20.500.14332/47264>
- Culhane, D., Fantuzzo, J., Hill, M., & Burnett, T. (2018). Maximizing the Use of Integrated Data Quality Campaign & The Early Childhood Data Collaborative. (2016). *Roadmap for early childhood and K-12 data linkages: Key areas to ensure quality implementation*. Data Quality Campaign. <https://dataqualitycampaign.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Roadmap-for-Early-Childhood-and-K12-Data-Linkages.pdf>
- Data Systems: Understanding the Challenges and Advancing Solutions. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 675(1), 221-239. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716217743441>
- Datnow, A., Lockton, M., & Weddle, H. (2021). Capacity building to bridge data use and instructional improvement through evidence on student thinking. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 69, 100869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100869>
- DeHart, D., & Shapiro, C. (2017). Integrated Administrative Data & Criminal Justice Research (2017). *American Journal of Criminal Justice* 42, 255 – 274.

<https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/integrated-administrative-data-criminal-justice-research>

deMonsabert, J., Brookes, S., Coffey, M. M., & Thornburg, K. (2021). Data use for continuous instructional improvement in early childhood education settings. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 49(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01168-3>

Draugalis, J. R., & Plaza, C. M. (2009). Best practices for survey research reports revisited: implications of target population, probability sampling, and response rate. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 73(8), 142.
<https://doi.org/10.5688/aj7308142>

Fixsen, D. L., Ward, C., Blase, K., Naoom, S., Metz, A., & Louison, L. (2018). *Assessing drivers best practices*. Active Implementation Research Network.
<https://www.activeimplementation.org>

Fixsen, D., Naoom, S., Blase, K., Friedman, R., Wallace, F. (2005). *Implementation research: A synthesis of the literature*. National Implementation Research Network.
<https://nirn.fpg.unc.edu/sites/nirn.fpg.unc.edu/files/resources/NIRN-MonographFull-01-2005.pdf>

Gibbs, L., Nelson, A. H., Dalton, E., Cantor, J., Shipp, S., & Jenkins, D. (2017). *IDS governance: Setting Up for Ethical and Effective Use*. National Association of Counties.
https://www.naco.org/sites/default/files/event_attachments/Governance.pdf

Green, J. C. (2007). *Mixed methods in social inquiry*. Jossey-Bass.

- Hendra, R., & Hill, A. (2019). Rethinking response rates: new evidence of little relationship between survey response rates and nonresponse bias. *Evaluation Review*, 43(5), 307-330. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193841X18807719>
- Kagan, S. L., & Gomez, R. E. (Eds.). (2015). *Early childhood governance. Choices and consequences*. Teachers college.
- Keller, S., Lancaster, V., & Shipp, S. (2017). Building Capacity for Data-Driven Governance: Creating a New Foundation for Democracy. *Statistics and Public Policy*, 4(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2330443X.2017.1374897>
- Kessel, K. A., Bohn, C., Engelmann, U., Oetzel, D., Bougatf, N., Bendl, R., ... & Combs, S. E. (2014). Five-year experience with setup and implementation of an integrated database system for clinical documentation and research. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 114(2), 206-217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2014.02.002>
- Kitzmiller, E. (2014). *IDS case study: University of South Florida - Fulfilling a Statewide Need to Enhance Policy Analysis and Service Delivery*. Actionable Intelligence for Social Policy. https://aisp.upenn.edu/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/PinellasCountyUSF_CaseStudy.pdf
- Kvale, S. (2006). Dominance through interviews and dialogues. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12, 480–500. doi:10.1177/1077800406286235
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.
- Little, M. H., Cohen-Vogel, L., Sadler, J., & Merrill, B. (2019). Data-driven decision making in early education: Evidence From North Carolina’s Pre-K program. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27, 18. <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.27.4198>

- Mandinach, E. B., & Jackson, S. (2012). *Transforming teaching and learning through data-driven decision making*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Mandinach, E. B., & Schildkamp, K. (2021). Misconceptions about data-based decision making in education: An exploration of the literature. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 69, 100842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100842>
- Maxwell, J. A. (2013). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- McGilvray, D. (2021). *Executing data quality projects* (2nd ed.). Academic Press/Elsevier.
- Metz, A., & Albers, B. (2014). What does it take? How federal initiatives can support the implementation of evidence-based programs to improve outcomes for adolescents. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 54(3), S92–S96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2013.11.025>
- Metz, A., & Bartley, L. (2012). Active implementation frameworks for program success. *Zero to three*, 32(4), 11-18.
- Metz, A., Bartley, L., Ball, H., Wilson, D., Naom, S., & Redmond, P. (2015). Active implementation frameworks for successful service delivery: Catawba County child wellbeing project. *Research on Social Work Practice*, 25(4), 415-422.
- Metz, A., Halle, T., Bartley, L., & Blasberg, A. (2013). The Key Components of successful implementation. In T. Halle, A. Metz, & I. Martinez-Beck, (Eds.), *Applying Implementation Science in Early Childhood Programs and Systems* (1st ed., pp. 21-42). Paul H. Brooks Publishing Company. <https://products.brookespublishing.com/Applying-Implementation-Science-in-Early-Childhood-Programs-and-Systems-P676.aspx>

Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2014). *Qualitative data analysis* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Nilsen, P. (2015). Making sense of implementation theories, models and frameworks. *Implementation Science* 10(53), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-015-0242-0>

Park, A. Y. (2021). What advances information sharing for sustainability performance management? Empirical evidence from US local governments. *Urban Governance*, 1(2), 72–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ugj.2022.01.001>

Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods* (4th edition). Sage Publications.

Petrila, J. (2018). Turning the law into a tool rather than a barrier to the use of administrative data for evidence-based policy. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 675(1), 67-82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000271621774108>

Project Management Institute. (2021). *A Guide to the project management body of knowledge (PMBOK® guide)* (7th ed.).

Regenstein, E. (2022). *The importance of modernizing technology in developing early childhood integrated data systems*. Foresight Law and Policy.

Saldaña, J. (2021). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Saunders, N.R., Janus, M., Porter, J., Lu, H., Gaskin, A., Kalappa, G., & Guttmann, A. (2021). Use of administrative record linkage to measure medical and social risk factors for early developmental vulnerability in Ontario, Canada. *International Journal of Population Data Science* 6(1), 1 – 19. <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v6i1.1407>

Sebastian-Coleman, L. (2022). *Data life cycle processes*. Academic Press/Elsevier

Sinclair, J., Davies, S., & Janus, M (2023). Student achievement trajectories in Ontario: Creating and validating a province-wide, multi-cohort and longitudinal database. *International Journal of Population Data Science*, 8(1), 1 – 14.

<https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v8i1.1843>

Sirinides, P., Coffey, M., & Dabbs (2024). *Implementation Capacity for Public Sector Integrated Data Systems*. Manuscript under review.

Susha, I., Rukanova, B., Zuiderwijk, A., Gil-Garcia, J. R., & Hernandez, M. G. (2023).

Achieving voluntary data sharing in cross sector partnerships: Three partnership models. *Information and Organization*, 33(1), 1 – 14.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infoandorg.2023.100448>

Tang, A., Rankin, P., Staton, S., and Thorpe, K. (2024). Access to high-quality early care and education: Analysis of Australia’s national integrated data. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 67, 352-362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2024.02.001>

Taylor, C.L., Christensen, D., Venn, A., Preen, D., Stafford, J. Hansen, E., Jose, K., & Zubrick, S. (2022). The Use of administrative record linkage to examine patterns of universal early childhood health and education service use from birth to Kindergarten (age 4 years) and developmental vulnerability in the Preparatory Year (age 5 years) in Tasmania, Australia. *International Journal of Population Data Science* 6(3), 1-13.

<https://doi.org/10.23889/ijpds.v6i3.1681>

Varier, D., & Yun, S. (2023). A review of research on assessment use: Implications for preparing early childhood educators for data-informed decision-making. *Journal of Early*

Childhood Teacher Education, 0(0), 1–26.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10901027.2023.2257157>

Walker, D. M., Hefner, J. L., DePuccio, M. J., Garner, J. A., Headings, A., Joseph, J. J., & Clark, A. (2022). Approaches for Overcoming Barriers to Cross-Sector Data Sharing. *American Journal of Managed Care*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.37765/ajmc.2022.88811>

Wu, M. J., Zhao, K., & Fils-Aime, F. (2022). Response rates of online surveys in published research: A meta-analysis. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 7, 100206.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2022.100206>

Zanti, S., Thomas, M.L. (2021) Evidence-based policymaking: What human service agencies can learn from implementation science and integrated data systems. *Global Implementation Research Applications 1*, 304–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43477-021-00028-x>

